

NFDI4Earth

Report

Learning more about Earth System Sciences users

Results of an online survey on discovery, publication, RDM challenges and areas of interests

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Executive Summary

The NFDI4Earth Academy hosts free and open online coffee lectures on key topics in Research Data Management (RDM) within the Earth System Sciences. While primarily aimed at Academy Fellows, these events are also accessible to the broader public.

The February coffee lecture featured a presentation on the OneStop4All portal. The OneStop4All serves as a central access point for Earth System Sciences resources and NFDI4Earth-developed services. Developed through a user-centered design process, the portal undergoes iterative feedback loops involving various stakeholders. The NFDI4Earth work program includes several feedback and landscaping activities. In this survey, attendees shared perspectives on key RDM topics and challenges, providing valuable input for refining our central services, e.g., the OneStop4All, and informing broader NFDI4Earth initiatives.

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Introduction

The NFDI4Earth Academy hosts free and open online coffee lectures on relevant topics in Research Data Management (RDM) within the Earth System Sciences. These lectures primarily target Academy Fellows, but are also open to the general public.

The coffee lecture on February 18, 2025, featured a presentation on the OneStop4All portal, delivered by NFDI4Earth Measures 2.1 and 4.3.

The OneStop4All portal serves as a central access point to key resources from the Earth System Sciences community and the services developed by NFDI4Earth. The portal is being developed incrementally through a user-centered design process, with multiple feedback loops to engage various stakeholders. NFDI4Earth's work program involves several activities aimed at gathering user needs and feedback, such as a survey on incentives for FAIR and open data practices¹, and investigations into the status of long-term preservation and archiving within the Earth System Sciences (ESS)². These activities are supported by regular gap analyses³ and trend scouting⁴, focusing on dedicated NFDI4Earth groups (e.g., incubator or pilot projects), which help shape the conceptualization of services like the OneStop4All.

As the current version of the OneStop4All emphasizes discovery, the coffee lecture provided an opportunity to gather insights on where attendees search for and publish their datasets, source code, and software. This information will help to ensure that the OneStop4All portal integrates relevant repositories, either in the repository search, the wizard or by harvesting repositories as data sources into the Knowledge Hub, thereby supporting dataset discovery within the portal.

Additionally, attendees were asked to share their perspectives on the most pressing research data management (RDM) topics and challenges they face. The results will be used to improve the structure and content of OneStop4All, as well as inform other relevant NFDI4Earth measures.

The survey was conducted using Zoom's polling feature. The following report sections are organized according to the questions using the same order as presented to the attendees.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12807203>

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11200016>

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8344438>

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10669825>

Where do you search or publish datasets?

The question on where the attendees search or publish datasets was implemented as an open question. The attendees' provided the following original responses:

Submission order	Original responses
1	Pangea
2	re3data, zenodo, forschungsdaten.info....
3	re3data.org
4	Pangaea
5	Zenodo
6	- institutional repository - World Data Centre - Zenodo
7	publish: institutional repository search: portals: e.g. Earth Data Repository
8	Pangaea for publication Copernicus for data search
9	data bases in my research field. or Google for data bases.
10	GFZ data services
11	PANGAEA
12	earth data portal

Table 1: Original responses to the question: "Where do you search or publish datasets?" ordered by attendees as submitted during the Coffee Lecture

The survey responses highlight a range of platforms used by researchers for dataset discovery and publication. In summarizing the responses, attendees use disciplinary and common search services, with PANGAEA⁵ (four times) and Zenodo (three times) being the most mentioned (see Figure 1). Thus, researchers seem to rely on institutional and domain-specific repositories for dataset publication, suggesting a preference for discipline-specific solutions over general-purpose repositories. While dedicated repositories are essential, researchers also use general search engines for discovering datasets, indicating a potential gap in repository findability and interoperability.

⁵ Information about PANGAEA as well as a sub-set of PANGAEA's datasets, relevant to the ESS community is available via the OneStop4All: <https://onestop4all.nfdi4earth.de/search?searchterm=PANGAEA&resourcetype=Dataset&resourcetype=Repository+%26+Archive&sort=>

Figure 1: Responses about where to search or publish datasets, ordered by services

Where do you publish software?

The question on where the attendees publish software was implemented as open question. The attendees' provided the following original responses:

Submission order	Original responses
1	GitLab
2	GitLab
3	GitHub
4	only internally (gitlab)
5	I didnt publish it
6	Github
7	Gitlab
8	Github
9	Github, OSF, Zenodo
10	Usually, I add the source code as supplementary material to the publication.
11	- institutional repository - institutional git - zenodo
12	Github, Zenodo
13	institutional repository or zenodo and software publication papers (e.g. GMD)

Submission order	Original responses
14	Github, Zenodo, own institutional Gitlab instance
15	git
16	GitHub and sometimes Bitbucket
17	gitHub
18	Thredds
19	did not publish code yet

Table 2: Original responses to the question: “Where do you publish software?”, ordered by attendees as submitted during the Coffee Lecture

Several platforms were mentioned multiple times, indicating their popularity for software publication. Most attendees publish their developed software on GitLab/GitHub, followed by Zenodo (or both) (see Figure 2), assuming that this is preferably used for long-term archiving and obtaining DOIs. Some researchers rely on institutional repositories or internal Git services, suggesting that some software remains unpublished or restricted to institutional access.

Figure 2: Responses about where to publish software, ordered by options

Which RDM topics are relevant to your research?

The question on relevant RDM topics was implemented as open question. The attendees' provided the following original responses:

Submission order	Original responses
1	Search, view and download geoscience datasets. where and how to publish dataset compilations belonging to a project
2	FAIR principles
3	metadata schematic
4	selecting a repo for our data, I dont know where to find a suitable one
5	Data curation, Metadata standardization
6	FAIR Data, Open source, data integration of different sources across research domains
7	OSF
8	data provenance and metadata scheme
9	e.g. Harmonized Metadata, Publication of large datasets, ...
10	reproducibility of workflows/code how to license own published datasets
11	To give researchers such RDM tasks that they also can fulfill in terms of skills and in terms to the tools and infrastructure we provide to them.
12	quality and integrity
13	storage
14	all topics along the data - lifecycle
15	publishing, searching and finding data(sets), meta-data

Table 3: Original responses to the question: “Which RDM topics are relevant to your research?”

The question received a diverse range of responses, highlighting key challenges and priorities in Research Data Management (RDM) within the Earth System Sciences. Attendees’ responses range from data characteristics, e.g., quality, size, or provenance, to the data lifecycle, such as searching, publishing, processing and storing data and commonly mention data discovery and accessibility, data publication and sharing, as well as metadata and standardisation (see Figure 3). With their responses, the researchers emphasized the need for efficient search tools and better guidance on selecting appropriate repositories. Publishing datasets in alignment with the FAIR principles remains a major concern, including licensing, dataset size limitations, and repository selection.

Figure 3: Responses about relevant RDM topics, clustered along topics as word cloud

What is your biggest RDM challenge in your research?

The question on attendees biggest RDM challenges was implemented as open question. The attendees' provided the following original responses:

Submission order	Original responses
1	not being a computer scientist and not knowing certain tools (GitLab, making code more efficient, security issues with code/data) and not receiving enough support from centre
2	Once we created ML ready datasets from public or own data how do we make them accessible
3	find and get datas
4	no solution(s) offered to choose from
5	keeping track of versions and what has happened to the data in between
6	Data integration and transformation of raw data into usable indicators.
7	data organization
8	use and maintenance of RDM infrstructure
9	Publication of large datasets & non-standardized metadata
10	actually implementing all the great recommendations in every day work... ;)

Submission order	Original responses
11	I am in admin. My biggest challenge is not to overemphasize and not to underemphasize the importance of RDM when talking to reseachers.
12	Visualisation and security
13	Obtaining the overview, what is possible, where to find and search for what ...
14	Size of raw data, NetCDF files with 500 GB or more

Table 4: Original responses to the question: “What is your biggest RDM challenge in your research?”

The responses highlight a variety of challenges, ranging from technical barriers to infrastructure limitations and practical implementation issues (see Figure 4). Some attendees struggle with RDM tools and concepts. Others face difficulties in discovering and accessing relevant datasets, highlighting the need for better search tools and centralized access points. Moreover, adopting best practices consistently in daily workflows still seems to be difficult.

Figure 4: Responses about RDM challenges, clustered along topics as word cloud

Summary

Overall, the survey responses indicate that researchers still face challenges across the entire data lifecycle, from discovery and storage to publication and metadata standardization. Addressing these needs will require a combination of technical

solutions, training, and policy development within the Earth System Sciences, such as those driven by NFDI4Earth.

The survey results highlight the need for improved repository selection support, better search and indexing mechanisms, and stronger integration between institutional, domain-specific, and global repositories. In the OneStop4All, there are several offerings, e.g., a repository wizard or data search functionality. However, dedicated usability tests should demonstrate the proper implementation according to the needs.

Furthermore, the results show a strong preference for publishing software in GitHub and GitLab, but also highlight that some researchers keep software unpublished or rely on institutional storage. Encouraging best practices in open-source software management, integration with Zenodo, and awareness of software publication options could significantly enhance software accessibility and impact.

The survey responses indicate that researchers still require better tools, clearer guidelines, and stronger institutional support for effective disciplinary RDM or need to find them more easily. Addressing these needs will be crucial for improving data accessibility, quality, and usability across disciplines.

While we have already gathered valuable user feedback for the OneStop4All, such as during the release event, plenary sessions, and interviews, we aim to further explore user needs and gather additional input through follow-up studies and recurring polls.